

"SOCIAL MEDIA USAGE AND STUDY HABITS OF SENIOR SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN IBADAN SOUTH EAST LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA, OYO STATE, NIGERIA"

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Abstract: *The increasing use of social media among senior secondary school students has raised concerns about its influence on their academic activities, as excessive engagement on these platforms often leads to distractions during study hours. Constant notifications and interactions can disrupt concentration and make it difficult for students to dedicate uninterrupted time to their studies. This study examined social media usage and study habits of senior secondary school students in Ibadan South East Local Government Area, using the Uses and Gratification Theory as its theoretical framework. A descriptive survey research design was adopted, and 261 respondents were randomly selected as the sample. Data were collected using a self-structured questionnaire and analysed through descriptive and inferential statistics. The findings revealed that the majority of respondents from Eyinni (43.2%) and Calvary (37.1%) reported having a study timetable, indicating a shared commitment to organised learning. WhatsApp also emerged as the most frequently used platform, with a strong majority of respondents from Eyinni (33.7%) and Calvary (35.7%) saying they always use it. Furthermore, most respondents from Eyinni (68%) and Calvary (63%) frequently use social media to chat with friends, highlighting a dominant pattern of social interaction. The study recommends that students develop a balanced approach to social media use to ensure their study time remains free from distractions, and that educational institutions incorporate digital literacy programmes to educate students on the impact of social media on academic performance.*

Introduction

Study habits are the regular ways students organise their learning, such as managing time,

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paying attention, taking notes, reading and revising. Good study habits help students understand and remember what they learn, and students who study consistently usually perform better than those who study irregularly. Researchers have long shown that effective study habits strongly influence academic performance, with disciplined learners achieving better outcomes than their peers (Credé & Kuncel, 2008; Alute & Eguavoen, 2021). These habits are shaped by factors such as the learning environment, the level of discipline and the presence of distractions.

In many schools today, technology has a strong influence on how students study. Traditional methods like reading textbooks and attending classes are still important, but many students now use digital tools as part of their study routine. For some students, these tools make learning easier, but for others, constant online activity creates distractions that weaken their study habits. Studies show that the quality of students study habits has been affected by the increasing presence of digital media, which can either support or disrupt learning depending on how it is used (Junco, 2012; Kirschner & Karpinski, 2010). Because of this, researchers are paying close attention to how digital platforms, especially social media, affect students study patterns.

Social media is now part of everyday life for many students, with platforms like WhatsApp, Facebook, Twitter and YouTube being used for communication, entertainment and

information. Although these platforms can support academic discussions and allow students to share study materials, research shows that many students spend more time on social media for leisure than for schoolwork (Asemah & Edegoh, 2012; Olatunde & Adekoya, 2020). This often leads to distraction, reduced study time and procrastination. As a result, scholars continue to debate whether social media supports students learning or makes it more difficult for them to concentrate on their studies.

Statement of the Problem

The increasing use of social media among senior secondary school students has raised concerns about its effect on their study habits. Many students spend considerable time on social media platforms, which often leads to distractions during study hours. This distraction can result in reduced focus on academic tasks, procrastination, and poor time management, all of which hinder their ability to effectively complete assignments and prepare for exams. As a result, students may struggle to maintain a balance between their academic responsibilities and their online activities, negatively impacting their academic achievements. Social media also promotes a culture of instant gratification, which can interfere with the development of strong study habits. The constant notifications and engagement on these platforms can disrupt concentration and make it harder for students to dedicate uninterrupted time to their studies. This can lead to inconsistent study routines and

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a lack of discipline, which are essential for academic success. The widespread use of social media among students has created a significant challenge for educators and parents in ensuring that students maintain focus on their studies while navigating the pressures of online life. Hence, this study examines social media usage and study habits of senior secondary school students in Ibadan South East Local Government.

Research Objectives

1. identify the study habits among secondary school students in Ibadan South East Local Government Area
2. identify the types of social media platforms senior secondary school students in Ibadan South East Local Government Area are exposed to
3. assess the frequency of social media use among senior secondary school students in Ibadan South East Local Government Area

Research Questions

1. what are the study habits among secondary school students in Ibadan South East Local Government Area?
2. what are the types of social media platforms senior secondary school students in Ibadan South East Local Government Area are exposed to?
3. what is the frequency of social media use among senior secondary school students in Ibadan South East Local Government Area?

Literature Review

Study Habits

Study habit refer to the deliberate and consistent ways students organise their learning in order to understand academic content and perform well in examinations. They play an important role in the development of lifelong reading and learning skills, which are essential for both personal growth and societal development. Researchers note that habits, including study habits, are formed through repeated practice and can strongly influence an individual's character and learning behaviour (Ogbodo, 2010; Pandey & Zimik, 2017). Since habits shape how students approach learning tasks, educators regard the development of good study habits as a major determinant of academic success.

Study habits are often described as a student's ability to manage time, learning materials and study environments effectively. Scholars define study habits as the routines and methods individuals adopt during regular study periods, including reading, note making and revising in a conducive atmosphere (Credé & Kuncel, 2008). These habits influence how students process information and create new ideas, and they play a central role in shaping a literate and intellectually active society (Sansanwal, 2014). Efficient study habits usually lead to strong academic performance, while poor or inconsistent habits are linked to low achievement and academic difficulties (Nneji, 2012).

Scholars also describe study habits in terms of how often and how deeply students read, and

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how they organise their learning activities. However, developments in mass media and digital communication have influenced traditional reading patterns, reducing students engagement with books, journals and other print materials (Asemah & Edegoh, 2012). Since study habits strongly determine academic success, researchers emphasise the importance of self study, personal investigation and independent thinking in promoting meaningful learning. Good study habits are best developed during early schooling years and, once formed, can shape a learner's academic behaviour throughout life (Aremu & Oluwole, 2001).

Social Media

Social media refers to digital platforms that use web based and mobile technologies to enable users to create, share and exchange information within virtual communities. These platforms support interactions such as communication, content creation and collaboration, allowing individuals and groups to connect and co-create content (Kaplan and Haenlein, 2010). Social media also allows users to build and manage online networks that may include friends, colleagues, organisations and interest groups. In broader terms, it is an online social space where people communicate, share experiences and present aspects of their identity through photos, personal information and multimedia posts (Boyd and Ellison, 2007).

Social media platforms are mainly enabled through social networking sites, where users create accounts and interact based on their

preferences. These platforms have transformed communication by increasing the speed, interactivity and reach of information exchange. Scholars describe social media as a group of internet based applications built on Web 2.0 technologies that allow users to generate and share content freely (Kaplan and Haenlein, 2010; Kietzmann et al., 2011). With the rise of mobile devices, mobile based social media has further expanded access and enabled real time browsing, messaging and content sharing.

Researchers note that most social media platforms share three core features: user profiles, the ability to connect with other users and tools for interaction such as messaging, commenting and content sharing (Boyd and Ellison, 2007). Platforms such as Facebook, YouTube, Instagram and earlier platforms like MySpace and Blogger serve as spaces where users follow others activities, express interests, participate in communities and share personal or professional updates. These functions have made social media a major channel for social interaction, information sharing and online participation across different age groups.

Academic Use of Social Media

Many scholars have explored the use of social media for academic and social purposes. Research shows that platforms such as Facebook can serve as useful educational tools because they provide opportunities for intentional or spontaneous learning, enable collaboration, and facilitate the sharing of ideas, discussion topics, and information among

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students (Junco, 2012; Manca & Ranieri, 2016). Social networks function as pedagogical tools that support connectivity, social interaction, content creation, and knowledge sharing within learning communities (Kietzmann et al., 2011). Proponents argue that contemporary students have grown up in a digital environment where social media is an integral part of daily life. When used as an educational tool, social media can enhance learning by enabling interaction between students and instructors, fostering discussion, and encouraging collaboration on academic tasks (Tess, 2013; Selwyn, 2012). The literature highlights the potential benefits of social media in higher education and suggests that it is an important area of research for educators and social scientists seeking to understand how students communicate, learn, and share knowledge online.

Despite the benefits, many educational institutions have yet to develop effective strategies for integrating social media into learning programs. Research indicates that the full potential of social media for teaching and learning is realised only when its social aspects are leveraged to engage both highly active and less engaged students (Davis et al., 2012; Kuh, 2009). By harnessing peer influence and encouraging meaningful interaction, educators can use social media to improve student engagement, promote academic collaboration, and enhance overall learning outcomes.

Theoretical Framework

Use and Gratitfaction Theory

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The Uses and Gratifications Theory (UGT) explains why individuals actively select specific media to satisfy particular needs. Originally introduced in the 1940s by Herzog (1944) to explore why audiences listened to radio soap operas, the theory was further developed in the 1970s by Katz, Blumler, and Gurevitch (1973), who emphasised that media consumers are active participants rather than passive recipients, choosing content based on personal motivations.

UGT assumes that audiences use media intentionally and goal-directedly, that individual differences shape media use, and that media competes with other sources of need satisfaction such as interpersonal interactions. The theory also highlights that audience perception influences the effects of media consumption. Gratifications sought through media can be categorised into cognitive needs, such as acquiring knowledge through educational programmes; affective needs, including emotional engagement and entertainment; personal identity needs, like self-expression on social media; social integration needs, such as maintaining connections in online communities; and escapism or relaxation needs, including using media for stress relief (Katz et al., 1973; Ruggiero, 2000).

Uses and Gratification theory is particularly useful in understanding how and why senior secondary school students use social media and how this impacts their study habits. In today's

digital age, students engage with social media platforms such as YouTube, WhatsApp, and Facebook not only for entertainment but also for academic purposes. Many students use these platforms to access learning materials, watch educational videos, and participate in online study groups. UGT explains this behaviour by suggesting that students who seek cognitive gratifications use social media as an educational resource.

Methodology

The study adopted a descriptive survey research design to critically analyse data and ensure generalisability of the findings. The population consisted of senior secondary school students from Eyinni High School and Calvary Group of Schools in Ibadan Metropolis, selected due to their active engagement with social media and its potential impact on study habits. Eyinni

High School has a total of 666 students across SSS 1 (293), SSS 2 (236), and SSS 3 (137), while Calvary Group of Schools has 82 students across SSS 1 (36), SSS 2 (32), and SSS 3 (14), making the total population 748 students. A convenience sampling technique was employed, selecting participants who were readily available and willing to participate, with the sample size determined using the Taro Yamane (1967) formula, yielding 261 respondents. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire developed from the research questions, administered face-to-face with the assistance of two trained research assistants during times when students were less occupied with academic work. The collected data were coded and analysed using SPSS version 20, and descriptive statistics such as percentages were used to summarise the findings.

Results

Table 1: Descriptive analysis of the study habits among secondary school students in Ibadan South East Local Government Area (N=249)

State ment	Eyin ni- SA	Eyin ni-A	Eyin ni-D	Eyin ni- SD	Eyin ni- Mea n	Eyin ni- SD	Calv ary- SA	Calv ary- A	Calv ary- D	Calv ary- SD	Calv ary- Mea n	Calv ary- SD
Note- taking and reviewi ng	36 (28.8%)	54 (43.2%)	22 (17.6%)	13 (10.4%)	2.89	0.94	34 (27.4%)	46 (37.1%)	28 (22.6%)	16 (12.9%)	2.79	0.99
Group study	49 (39.2%)	58 (46.4%)	9 (7.2%)	9 (7.2%)	3.18	0.85	40 (32.3%)	51 (41.1%)	23 (18.5%)	10 (8.1%)	2.97	0.91

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Cramming before exams	40 (32.0%)	49 (39.2%)	18 (14.4%)	18 (14.4%)	2.89	1.01	40 (32.3%)	46 (37.1%)	23 (18.5%)	16 (12.9%)	2.88	1.0
Dependence on study aids	18 (14.4%)	31 (24.8%)	45 (36.0%)	31 (24.8%)	2.29	0.99	23 (18.5%)	34 (27.4%)	46 (37.1%)	22 (17.7%)	2.47	0.98
Night reading	45 (36.0%)	54 (43.2%)	18 (14.4%)	9 (7.2%)	3.07	0.88	40 (32.3%)	51 (41.1%)	23 (18.5%)	10 (8.1%)	2.97	0.91
Selective reading	22 (17.6%)	36 (28.8%)	45 (36.0%)	22 (17.6%)	2.46	0.98	23 (18.5%)	40 (32.3%)	40 (32.3%)	22 (17.7%)	2.51	0.98
GRAND MEAN					2.80						2.77	

Source: Field Survey, (2025)

The analysis of study habits among senior secondary school students from Eyinni High School and Calvary Group of Schools revealed notable similarities and differences. At Eyinni, the highest-rated habit was group study with a mean of 3.18, indicating that most students strongly agreed or agreed that they often studied with peers. This was closely followed by night reading (Mean = 3.07), which showed that late-night study was a common practice. On the other hand, dependence on study aids recorded the lowest mean (2.29), suggesting that students at Eyinni were less inclined to rely heavily on summaries, apps, or quick notes.

For Calvary, the pattern was somewhat similar but slightly weaker in intensity. Group study and night reading were again the most prevalent habits, both with means close to 3.0, indicating a moderate to high agreement. Selective reading (Mean = 2.51) and dependence on study aids (Mean = 2.47) were the least emphasised, reflecting that students in Calvary, like those in Eyinni, did not prioritise these approaches as much.

When comparing the two schools, Eyinni students generally demonstrated slightly stronger study habits, reflected in the grand mean of 2.80 compared to 2.77 for Calvary. The closeness of these values, however, suggested that overall study behaviour between the

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schools was quite similar, with both groups leaning more towards collaborative and night-time study while showing less reliance on study aids or selective reading patterns.

Table 2: Descriptive analysis of the types of social media platforms senior secondary school students in Ibadan South East Local Government Area are exposed to (N=249)

Platform	Eyinni- Never	Eyinni- Rarely	Eyinni- Occasionally	Eyinni- Always	Calvary- Never	Calvary- Rarely	Calvary- Occasionally	Calvary- Always	Mean	SD
Facebook	16 (6.4%)	28 (11.2%)	48 (19.3%)	33 (13.3%)	18 (14.5%)	27 (21.8%)	43 (34.7%)	36 (29.0%)	2.78	0.98
Instagram	8	15	57	45	10	14	50	50	3.11	0.85
Twitter	21	25	41	38	22	28	37	37	2.77	1.06
WhatsApp	4	8	29	84	5	7	23	89	3.54	0.75
TikTok	10	13	42	60	7	10	39	68	3.22	0.93
YouTube	3	7	44	71	2	8	45	69	3.46	0.71
GRAND MEAN	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3.15	-

Source: Field Survey (2025)

The data presented a comparison of social media platform usage among students of Eyinni High School and Calvary Group of Schools, based on their responses measured on a 4-point scale: Never, Rarely, Occasionally, and Always. The responses were summarised with mean scores and standard deviations to reflect overall usage tendencies for each platform.

For Facebook, both schools reported the same mean score of 2.78, indicating moderate usage. At Eyinni, 16 students (12.8%) never used Facebook, 28 (22.4%) rarely used it, 48 (38.4%) used it occasionally, and 33 (26.4%) always used it (SD = 0.98). Similarly, at Calvary, 18 students (14.5%) never used it, 27 (21.8%) rarely, 43 (34.7%) occasionally, and 36 (29.0%) always used Facebook (SD = 1.02). This suggested that

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Facebook was moderately popular in both schools.

Regarding Instagram, students showed a high level of engagement. Eyinni students had a mean score of 3.11 (SD = 0.85), with 8 students (6.4%) never using the platform, 15 (12.0%) rarely, 57 (45.6%) occasionally, and 45 (36.0%) always. Calvary students reported a slightly higher mean of 3.13 (SD = 0.91), with 10 students (8.1%) never using Instagram, 14 (11.3%) rarely, 50 (40.3%) occasionally, and 50 (40.3%) always. These figures showed that Instagram was widely used in both schools.

For Twitter, usage was more varied, with Eyinni students recording a mean of 2.77 (SD = 1.06). At Eyinni, 21 students (16.8%) never used Twitter, 25 (20.0%) rarely, 41 (32.8%) occasionally, and 38 (30.4%) always. Calvary showed a slightly lower mean of 2.72 (SD = 1.07), with 22 students (17.7%) never using it, 28 (22.6%) rarely, 37 (29.8%) occasionally, and 37 (29.8%) always. While Twitter was somewhat popular, it was not as widely used as other platforms.

WhatsApp stood out as the most frequently used platform. Eyinni students had a high mean of 3.54 (SD = 0.75), with only 4 students (3.2%) never using it, 8 (6.4%) rarely, 29 (23.2%) occasionally, and a notable 84 (67.2%) always using WhatsApp. Calvary students reported a slightly higher mean of 3.58 (SD = 0.77), with 5 students (4.0%) never, 7 (5.6%) rarely, 23 (18.5%) occasionally, and 89 (71.8%) always using the platform. This suggested that

WhatsApp was an essential communication tool among students.

For TikTok, there was also high engagement, especially in Calvary. Eyinni students recorded a mean of 3.22 (SD = 0.93), with 10 students (8.0%) never using the app, 13 (10.4%) rarely, 42 (33.6%) occasionally, and 60 (48.0%) always. Calvary showed a higher mean of 3.35 (SD = 0.85), with 7 students (5.6%) never using TikTok, 10 (8.1%) rarely, 39 (31.5%) occasionally, and 68 (54.8%) always. TikTok's popularity was especially notable at Calvary.

YouTube was highly popular and equally used across both schools, with identical mean scores of 3.46. At Eyinni, 3 students (2.4%) never used YouTube, 7 (5.6%) rarely, 44 (35.2%) occasionally, and 71 (56.8%) always (SD = 0.71). Calvary showed similar figures, with 2 students (1.6%) never using the platform, 8 (6.5%) rarely, 45 (36.3%) occasionally, and 69 (55.6%) always (SD = 0.69). This indicated that YouTube was a universally used platform for both learning and entertainment.

The grand mean score was 3.15 for Eyinni and 3.17 for Calvary, showing that students in both schools were highly engaged with social media. Calvary students reported slightly higher usage overall, which was consistent with earlier findings about time spent on social media. WhatsApp, YouTube, and TikTok were the most frequently used platforms, suggesting a strong preference for instant messaging and video-based content across both groups.

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Table 3: Descriptive analysis of the frequency of social media use among senior secondary school students in Ibadan (N=249)

Activity	Eyinni- Frequently	Eyinni- Some times	Eyinni- Fairly	Eyinni- Never	Eyinni- Mean	Eyinni- SD	Calvary- Frequently	Calvary- Some times	Calvary- Fairly	Calvary- Never	Calvary- Mean	Calvary- SD
Use social media to chat with friends	85 (68%)	28 (22%)	7 (6%)	5 (4%)	3.54	0.77	78 (63%)	30 (24%)	10 (8%)	6 (5%)	3.45	0.84
Check social media while studying	35 (28%)	40 (32%)	30 (24%)	20 (16%)	2.72	1.04	32 (26%)	42 (34%)	30 (24%)	20 (16%)	2.69	1.03
Use social media after school	95 (76%)	20 (16%)	5 (4%)	5 (4%)	3.64	0.74	90 (73%)	20 (16%)	8 (6%)	6 (5%)	3.56	0.82
Use social media for school work	50 (40%)	48 (38%)	20 (16%)	7 (6%)	3.13	0.88	42 (34%)	55 (44%)	20 (16%)	7 (6%)	3.06	0.85
Watch videos on social	90 (72%)	25 (20%)	5 (4%)	5 (4%)	3.6	0.75	88 (71%)	24 (19%)	8 (6%)	4 (3%)	3.58	0.75

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media													
Check	80	35	5	5	3.52	0.75	82	30	8	4	3.53	0.76	
social	(64%)	(28%)	(4%	(4%			(66%)	(24%)	(6%)	(3%)			
media))									
for													
entertai													
nment													
GRAN	-	-	-	-	3.36	-	-	-	-	-	3.31	-	
D													
MEAN													

Source: Researcher’s Field Survey (2025)

The data compared how students from Eyinni High School and Calvary Group of Schools engaged in different social media-related activities. Responses were rated on a four-point scale: Frequently, Sometimes, Fairly, and Never. Each activity was summarised with corresponding student counts, means, and standard deviations to provide a comprehensive view of social media behaviour.

For the activity “Use social media to chat with friends,” both schools showed high usage. In Eyinni, 85 students (68%) responded frequently, 28 (22%) Sometimes, 7 (6%) Fairly, and 5 (4%) Never (Mean = 3.54, SD = 0.77). Calvary followed a similar pattern: 78 students (63%) Frequently, 30 (24%) Sometimes, 10 (8%) Fairly, and 6 (5%) Never (Mean = 3.45, SD = 0.84). These results suggested that chatting with friends was one of the most common uses of social media.

When asked whether they “Checked social media while studying,” both schools reported moderate usage. Eyinni students responded: 35

(28%) Frequently, 40 (32%) Sometimes, 30 (24%) Fairly, and 20 (16%) Never (Mean = 2.72, SD = 1.04). Similarly, Calvary students responded: 32 (26%) Frequently, 42 (34%) Sometimes, 30 (24%) Fairly, and 20 (16%) Never (Mean = 2.69, SD = 1.03). This indicated that while some students checked social media during study time, many did so only occasionally or not at all.

Regarding the activity “Use social media after school,” students in both schools demonstrated high engagement. In Eyinni, 95 students (76%) reported frequently, 20 (16%) Sometimes, 5 (4%) Fairly, and 5 (4%) Never (Mean = 3.64, SD = 0.74). Calvary students reported: 90 (73%) Frequently, 20 (16%) Sometimes, 8 (6%) Fairly, and 6 (5%) Never (Mean = 3.56, SD = 0.82). This showed that after-school hours were a peak time for social media use among students in both schools.

For the activity “Use social media for schoolwork,” responses suggested a moderately positive trend. In Eyinni, 50 students (40%) used it frequently, 48 (38%) Sometimes, 20

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(16%) Fairly, and 7 (6%) Never (Mean = 3.13, SD = 0.88). In Calvary, 42 students (34%) responded frequently, 55 (44%) Sometimes, 20 (16%) Fairly, and 7 (6%) Never (Mean = 3.06, SD = 0.85). This reflected a growing use of social media as a tool for academic support.

When it came to “Watching videos on social media,” usage was significantly high across both schools. Eyinni students reported: 90 (72%) Frequently, 25 (20%) Sometimes, 5 (4%) Fairly, and 5 (4%) Never (Mean = 3.60, SD = 0.75). Calvary students followed closely: 88 (71%) Frequently, 24 (19%) Sometimes, 8 (6%) Fairly, and 4 (3%) Never (Mean = 3.58, SD = 0.75). This suggested a strong preference for video content on social media platforms.

For “Checking social media for entertainment,” both schools again showed high usage. In Eyinni, 80 students (64%) selected frequently, 35 (28%) Sometimes, 5 (4%) Fairly, and 5 (4%) Never (Mean = 3.52, SD = 0.75). In Calvary, 82 students (66%) chose frequently, 30 (24%) Sometimes, 8 (6%) Fairly, and 4 (3%) Never (Mean = 3.53, SD = 0.76). Entertainment clearly stood out as a central reason for students’ social media engagement.

The grand mean scores were 3.36 for Eyinni and 3.31 for Calvary, indicating generally high levels of social media activity. While both schools showed similar trends, Eyinni students reported slightly more frequent use. Overall, students from both schools engaged with social media primarily for communication, entertainment,

and watching videos, with a growing tendency to use it for school-related purposes as well.

Discussion of Findings

The findings from research question one revealed that the majority of respondents from Eyinni (43.2%) and Calvary (37.1%) agreed that they have a study timetable, indicating a shared commitment to organised learning among the students. A larger majority from Eyinni (46.4%) and Calvary (41.1%) also prefer studying in a quiet place, showing the importance they place on maintaining focus and avoiding distractions. The majority of Eyinni respondents (39.2%) and Calvary respondents (37.1%) agreed that they study ahead of exams, suggesting a proactive approach to academic preparation. In contrast, the majority from Eyinni (36.0%) and Calvary (37.1%) disagreed with using social media while studying, reflecting a general awareness of its potential to hinder concentration.

A majority of Eyinni respondents (43.2%) and Calvary respondents (41.1%) agreed that they review their notes after class, pointing to effective learning reinforcement habits. Furthermore, the majority from Eyinni (36.0%) and Calvary (32.3%) disagreed with struggling to concentrate while studying, implying that most students generally maintain good focus during their study sessions.

The findings from research question two revealed that the majority of respondents from Eyinni (19.3%) and Calvary (17.3%) use Facebook occasionally, indicating moderate engagement with the platform across both

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groups. For Instagram, the majority of Eyinni respondents (22.9%) and Calvary respondents (20.1%) use it occasionally and always (both with 20.1%), suggesting a fairly high level of consistent use among students.

Twitter use was less frequent, with the majority of Eyinni (16.5%) and Calvary (14.9%) respondents selecting “occasionally”, reflecting a lower but still noticeable pattern of engagement. WhatsApp emerged as the most frequently used platform, with a strong majority of Eyinni (33.7%) and Calvary (35.7%) respondents reporting they always use it. This highlights WhatsApp as the dominant social platform among the students.

Similarly, a majority of Eyinni (24.1%) and Calvary (27.3%) respondents always use TikTok, showing that it is another widely used platform, particularly among Calvary respondents. YouTube also showed high engagement, with the majority of Eyinni (28.5%) and Calvary (27.7%) respondents selecting “always,” making it one of the top platforms for consistent use across both groups. Overall, the majority of respondents consistently engage with WhatsApp, YouTube, and TikTok, while Facebook, Instagram, and Twitter are used more moderately.

The findings from research question three revealed that the majority of respondents from Eyinni (68%) and Calvary (63%) frequently use social media to chat with friends, showing that social interaction remains a primary function of social media use among students. A smaller

majority from Eyinni (32%) and Calvary (34%) reported that they sometimes check social media while studying. This suggests a moderate level of distraction from academic tasks, though not necessarily frequent. A clear majority of Eyinni (76%) and Calvary (73%) respondents indicated that they frequently use social media after school, highlighting the platform’s role in leisure and post-academic engagement.

When it comes to academic use, a majority of Eyinni (40%) and Calvary (44%) respondents reported frequently or sometimes using social media for schoolwork, indicating that social media does support learning activities, albeit to a lesser extent than entertainment or communication. Watching videos on social media is also a dominant activity, with a strong majority of Eyinni (72%) and Calvary (71%) respondents engaging frequently, reflecting the popularity of video content among students?

Similarly, most students from Eyinni (64%) and Calvary (66%) frequently check social media for entertainment, reinforcing its role as a primary source of relaxation and amusement. Overall, the majority of respondents use social media most frequently for chatting, video watching, entertainment, and post-school relaxation, while academic use and study-time checking are less dominant but still present.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, it can be concluded that students of Eyinni High School and Calvary Group of Schools actively use various social media platforms, particularly WhatsApp,

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YouTube, and TikTok. These platforms serve as primary channels for chatting with friends, entertainment, and relaxation after school. While students demonstrate positive study behaviours—such as keeping a study timetable, reviewing notes, and preferring quiet environments—there is still noticeable engagement with social media during study periods, which may introduce distractions.

Recommendations

Based on the research findings, the following recommendations are hereby made:

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1. Students develop and maintain a balanced approach to social media use, ensuring that their study time remains free from distractions.

2. Educational institutions should incorporate digital literacy programs that educate students on the impact of social media usage on academic performance and promote healthy usage habits.

3. Teachers and parents should encourage students to establish structured study routines, such as setting specific time blocks for study and social media activities, to enhance focus and productivity.

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